

RESCUER

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Showing the way to the future of Emergency Responders

SIGNALS

COLLECTION

Enhanced hearing

Robust vision in adverse conditions

Augmented olfaction

Remote touch ((g)) Radar sensing

TRANSDUCTION

Augmented sense collection and transduction

Smart sensing framework

PROCESSING

Situation-aware information prioritization

Cognitive load balancing

Biosignals monitoring

COMMUNICATION

Ad hoc FRs communication

Seamless communication with Command & control

PERCEPTION

Augmented reality interfaces

Long term monitoring of exposure to hazardous environment

Black box for buildings

Perception of wireless devices for victim localization

Signs of life detection

Visual based self-localization

Inertial based localization

Galileo- assisted localization

 @H2020Rescuer

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